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“FROM STRUGGLES TO SUMMITS”

Beneath his smile, stories remain,
Of days filled with hunger, of nights spent in pain.
Yet through the hardship, he held on tight,
Carrying dreams that burned so bright.

A young boy stood by the schoolyard gate,
Selling ice candy while scouts marched in fate.
No uniform, no scarf to tie,
Yet his spirit soared, reaching the sky.

Hand-me-down pants—first too tight, then too wide,
His classmates laughed, but he wore them with pride.
For stitched in those seams was a quiet vow,
To rise above, to make it somehow.

With a hundred pesos, he learned the art
Of stretching coins, of a thrifty heart.
By Wednesday noon, his pockets were bare,
Yet he kept moving, refusing despair.

Long nights spent reading, eyes heavy yet keen,
Chasing a future he had never seen.
He stumbled, he struggled, but never let go,
Knowing one day, his light would glow.

From ice candy sales to a scholar's might,
From whispered prayers to standing in light.
He broke through walls, he climbed the steep,
Proving that dreams are ours to keep.

Now, he stands tall, a guiding hand,
For those who struggle to understand—

That every challenge, every fight,
Leads to victory, bathed in light.

At the peak, where few have been,
Lies the truth—**we're stronger than we've ever seen.**

